

SIPEXI: Placebo-controlled clinical trial of incobotulinumtoxinA for sialorrhea in children

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Supplemental Methods

Study design

Randomization

Patients aged 6-17 years were randomized (2:1) to receive incobotulinumtoxinA (incoBoNT/A) or placebo during the main period (MP). Randomization was performed with the randomization program RANCODE (Version 3.6, IDV Datenanalyse und Versuchsplanung, Gauting, Germany) for the placebo-controlled MP (only 6-17-year-old patients). An interactive web response system allocated a randomization number and uniquely numbered medication to each subject.

Blinding

For the double-blind MP, all medication vials (active/placebo) had the same appearance and their identity remained unknown to all staff involved in the study. The blind was only broken after database closure.

Dosing and injections

Patients assigned to incoBoNT/A received body weight (BW)-dependent total doses of 20 to 75 U per session. For patients weighing <30 kg, doses were determined

according to a dosing scheme of 5 weight classes ($12 < 15$, $\geq 15 < 19$, $\geq 19 < 23$, $\geq 23 < 27$, $\geq 25 < 30$ kg), with a defined dose per class (see Table 1). This resulted in mean doses between 1.3 U and 2.2 U/kg. Patients weighing ≥ 30 kg received a fixed dose of 75 U. The total dose was distributed in a 3:2 ratio among all parotid and submandibular glands (4 injections per session). As incoBoNT/A was dissolved in a fixed volume (at 25 U/mL), dose adjustment was performed by adapting the volumes (parotid injections: 0.24 mL to 0.9 mL each; submandibular injections: 0.16 mL to 0.6 mL each). Patients in the placebo arm received equivalent volumes of placebo solution (0.9% sodium chloride, sucrose, human serum albumin).

Dose reductions were permitted in the 3rd and 4th treatment cycle, if necessary due to treatment-emergent adverse events (AEs).

Table 1: Dosing scheme

Body weight [kg]	Parotid gland, each side		Submandibular gland, each side	
	Total dose per gland [units]	Volume per injection [ml]	Total dose per gland [units]	Volume per injection [ml]
≥ 12 to < 15	6	0.24	4	0.16
≥ 15 to < 19	9	0.36	6	0.24
≥ 19 to < 23	12	0.48	8	0.32
≥ 23 to < 27	15	0.60	10	0.40
≥ 27 to < 30	18	0.72	12	0.48
≥ 30	22.5	0.90	15	0.60

Outcome measures

Unstimulated salivary flow rate

The unstimulated salivary flow rate (uSFR, g/min) was determined by the swab method of direct saliva collection, which has been previously described for adults.¹

Two absorbent swabs (instead of four for adults) were placed in the oral cavity and their weight increase over 5 min was measured. This was repeated and the average uSFR was calculated. The uSFR was not determined in 2-5-year-olds because the method was considered inappropriate for this group.

Carers' global impression of change scale

Carers provided a rating on the global impression of change scale (GICS; 7-point Likert scale ranging from -3 [*very much worse*] to +3 [*very much improved*]), in response to the question: "*Compared to how the child was doing just before the last injection into his/her salivary gland, what is your overall impression of how he/she is functioning now as a result of this treatment?*". Where appropriate, carer and child decided on the rating together.

Other endpoints

Carers and investigators both rated the severity of the patients' drooling on the modified Teacher's drooling scale (mTDS), a 9-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (*dry, never drools*) to 9 (*profuse, clothing, hands, and objects become wet frequently*).²

Additionally, the drooling quotient (DQ) was calculated, reflecting the percentage of time a patient drooled.³ For this, the presence or absence of saliva was documented every 15 seconds for 10 min. The DQ was calculated by dividing the number of drooling episodes per session by 40 and multiplying by 100, then averaged over 2 sessions.

Adverse events

All AEs were coded with MedDRA (Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities) version 22.0. AEs of special interest (AESIs), including dysphagia, aspiration, pneumonia aspiration and others, were actively questioned at each visit. Vital signs, body mass index (BMI), and blood samples were assessed. Oral health was

examined by a dentist, and dental/periodontal AEs were evaluated. In line with recommendations for blood sampling in pediatric populations,⁴ blood collection for anti-botulinum toxin antibody tests was only performed in patients aged 6-17 years weighing at least 30 kg.

Statistical analysis

Details of sample size determination

A total of 219 patients aged 6-17 years were planned to be randomized. This was driven by considerations regarding the co-primary efficacy variable “change in uSFR from baseline to week 4”, based on a study in children with sialorrhea by Jongerius *et al.*,⁵ which showed a mean change (with standard deviation [SD]) in drooling of -0.16 (0.19) mL/min (mg/min due to 1.0 g/mL gravity of saliva) from baseline to week 4 for BoNT/A. This included a “missing” rate of $\sim 23\%$. Thus, a conservative estimate of -0.05 (0.22) mL/min was assumed for the sample size consideration. For the co-primary variable “GICS at week 4”, no reference data were available. The sample of 219 patients was sufficient to provide 95% power to detect a statistically significant difference in treatment means of 1.0 point with an SD of 1.93.

Details of statistical modelling

The confirmatory analysis of the co-primary variables was a mixed model repeated measures (MMRM) analysis (two-sided, significance level $\alpha=0.05$) with comparison of least squares (LS) means between incoBoNT/A and placebo, performed on the FAS, limited to patients aged 6-17 years. The dependent variables were the change in uSFR from baseline to week 4 and the carers’ GICS rating at week 4. The independent variables were defined as treatment group, pooled investigation site, and age group as fixed factors, visit*treatment as interaction term,

and visit as repeated factor. The variable “pooled investigation site” comprised the groups “Georgia/Russia”, “Hungary/Poland/Serbia”, and “Ukraine” and “age group” included the groups “6-9 years”, “10-12 years”, and “13-17 years”. To adjust for baseline status, the MMRM of the uSFR change additionally included the baseline uSFR as covariate. As no baseline of the GICS was available, the baseline carers’ mTDS was used as covariate in the MMRM model for the GICS rating.

References

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